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Measurement Campaign on 5G Indoor millimeter Wave and Visible Light Communications Multi Component Carrier System

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Abstract— This paper presents the technical performance results of a measurement campaign from a 5G Indoor millimeter Wave (mmWave) and Visible Light Communications (VLC) Multi Component Carrier System, which was developed in a Horizon 2020 research project called Internet of Radio-Light (IoRL). The measurement campaign was performed in the famous Integer House laboratory at the Innovation Park in Building Research Establishment in Watford, UK, which represents a typical European home environment. It includes four field test results: 1) VLC Received Signal Quality measured as Error Vector Magnitude against Coverage, 2) mmWave Received Signal Quality measured as Error Vector Magnitude against Coverage, 3) VLC Location Accuracy against a prescribed grid using Received Signal Strength, 4) Comparison of Measured and Simulated Electromagnetic Field (EMF) strength against coverage. This measurement campaign not only tests the system concept in a realistic indoor home environment but also provides analysis of the results with practical recommendations on further technical enhancements required to improve the system performance and insights into viable commercial solutions and applications. Other environments in which this technology could be deployed were envisaged as: underground train platforms and tunnels, museums and supermarkets.

Index Terms— 5G indoor millimeter Wave and Visible Light Communications, 5G multicomponent carrier system, Visible Light Communication indoor location accuracy, simulated and measured Electromagnetic Field strength against coverage.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE high demand in the usage of wireless communications in buildings is causing interference and congestion, whereas the propagation of Radio Frequency (RF) waves are being restricted by the modern building materials. Thus, there has been an interest in the deployment of cellular home networks (HeNBs) by the building owners as HeNBs operate in licensed spectrum, meaning they can avoid congestion and interference. However, the deployment of the HeNBs requires the approval of Mobile Network Operators (MNO) as a result of the possible interference to the outside transmitted signal from the main mobile network (eNB). Thus, every building that requires the deployment of a HeNB needs each own MNO to provide the approval for it, which makes it very inconvenient and costly for building owners.

Since the IoRL project operates in an unlicensed 60 GHz mmWave and visible light spectrum, it offers a solution for providing 5G HgNB (Home gNB) broadband without the approval of MNOs, since the propagation characteristics of EM waves using the mentioned spectrum do not interfere with the transmitted outside 5G signal whilst also offering a widespread broadband coverage within buildings, as it uses the radio-light access points, which are installed within the lighting system in the buildings. The high costs of electronic components required for developing a 60 GHz system, meant that it would have restricted the development of the demonstration to only one single Remote Radio Head (RRH), thereby restricting our ability to develop a Time Difference of Arrival (TDoA) location estimation system since at least four RRHs are required for computing location. Instead, a 40 GHz system was developed, as it is cheaper than the 60 GHz and all the electronic components needed were widely available. This was developed as it would be able to provide a proof of principle system for four or more RRHs.

This proof of principle system was tested at the Innovation Park in the Building Research Establishment Watford, UK. The Innovation Park features full-scale demonstration buildings that have been developed by industry partners, which display innovative design, materials and technologies that combine to address the development challenges facing regions across the world. Technology demonstration, research, testing, training and dissemination are key activities which underpin the operation and development of the Innovation Park, thus making it the ideal place to demonstrate the Internet of Radio Light system in a home scenario in its famous Integer House, which has been showcasing new home technology for over 20 years. All the numerical results of the VLC and mmWave measurement campaign are available on Zenodo database [16] and data from the EM Exposure Simulation are available on Zenodo database [17].

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the system architecture. Section III details the experimental setup for the technical tests. Section IV describes the experimental procedure to practically evaluating coverage and localization performance. Section V provides the results of the field tests. In Section VI presents the details of the mmWave EMF exposure test results. In Section VII provides analysis of results for VLC coverage and location accuracy, mmWave Coverage and EMF exposure. Section VIII. Section IX provides conclusions.

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II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The IoRL layered architecture consists of four layers namely: Service, Network Function Virtualisation (NFV), Software Defined Network (SDN) and Access layer, as shown in Figure 1.

The Service layer refers to various services on the data centre server-side, including geolocation multimedia services, databases, security services...etc. the preliminary design of the IoRL hosts back-end services on a multi-core Multiaccess Edge Computing (MEC) Cloud Server. To achieve successful interaction with back-end services, User Equipment (UE) runs front-end mobile applications on the UE device i.e. Smart Phones, Tablet PCs, Virtual Reality Headsets and HDTVs.

The NFV layer refers to deploying the network functions in the form of NFVs exploiting VNF technologies. Deploying IoRL services in such format enables resource slicing which in turn offers higher resource utilization by hosting end-user services, network services and third-party services on the same hardware resources. OpenStack Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM) was utilized to enable the NFV layer.

The SDN Layer refers to the networking paradigm utilized in the IoRL. SDN layer entails SDN Forwarding Devices (FDs) that routes IP packets to/from their 5G Layer 2/3 Protocol Processors, SDN Controller that is integrated within Neutron project of OpenStack and the SDN applications that offer the logical intelligence of the network. The Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator (NFVO) invokes various virtual functions required for an Intelligent Home IP Gateway such as Access & Mobility Management, Deep Packet Inspection and Network Security Functions.

The Access Layer consists of up to 32 RRLH Controllers. Each RRLH Controller drives up to four VLC and mmWave RRLH pairs all transmitting the same Transmission Block Sub-Frame, thereby providing a Multiple Input Single Output (MISO) transmission on downlink paths and Single Input Multiple Output (SIMO) on uplink paths for its coverage area, which is typically a room or floor areas of a building.

Each room or floor area in a building can be provisioned by a single RRLH Controller with its group of RRLHs and intra-building handover performed between these areas with the aid of VLC and mmWave location sensing application that continuously records the positions of UE in the building.

A UE can either obtain direct access to the Internet, by only using 5G protocols on the Access Layer interface to the UE, to deliver IP packets to the Network Layer and thence to the Server Applications in the Service Layer or obtain access to the Mobile Network Operator's (MNO) Evolved Packet Core (EPC)/5G Core (5GC), by using 5G protocols on the Access Layer interfaces to both the UE and EPC/5GC, to deliver IP packets to the Network Layer and thence to the applications supported by the MNO. This latter approach allows applications, such as Facebook, on a Smart phone to be accessed on both the outside Mobile Network as well as the Intelligent Home Network with handover between them. The VNFs on the NFV Layer identify the destination of IP packets

and the SDN Controller directs these IP packets to their appropriate destination.

Therefore, our proposed solution enables the building owner to have connectivity to different operators to facilitate the use of different devices registered with different operators, as well as exploiting the license free spectrum for accessing the home network.

Figure 1: IoRL Layered Architecture

The Access Layer architecture uses a 10G Common Public Radio Interface ring Ethernet, to interconnect a Distributed Radio Access Network (DRAN) processor with up to 32 Remote Radio Light Head (RRLH) Controllers each hosting two Lower Layer 1 processors, the first that generates an IF signal to drive up to 4 VLC MISO modules using a 1 to 4 RF splitter and a second that generates an IF signal to drive or be driven by up to 4 mmWave RF Duplex modules using a 1 to 4 RF splitter. The functional split between the RRLH Remote Radio Unit and the DRAN in the Physical Layer is in-line with option 7 of the e-CPRI architecture. The Upper PHY layer unit includes the interface with the MAC and upper RAN layers and mainly includes the FEC encoders (LDPC and Polar), decoders and drive over the 10Gbps Ethernet ring the data units along with their related control descriptors destined to the RRLH Controller units. The 10Gbps Ethernet ring can be looped from room to room in a building from one RRLH to another in a similar way to the electric light circuit in a home. A 10 MHz GPS reference is sent to DRAN and RRLH Controller and UE for use in 5G synchronization algorithms at these layers.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The 5G multicomponent carrier indoor system contains 6 main components for both VLC and mmWave measurement campaign [1]. 1) A 5G base station including PHY Layer Central Unit, named DRAN (Distributed Radio Access Network) and RRLH Control Units. DRAN is carrying out the tasks of the L1 upper layer, which mainly include the FEC encoding and decoding, beam management, distribution of the data to the RRLHs over the 10 Gbps Ethernet rings and the

interface with the MAC and higher layers. RRLH Control Units are responsible for the major part of the PHY layer processing. Processing includes mainly the data modulation/demodulation, precoding, IFFT, air interface resource mapping, and antenna/LED management. These units' interface on one side with the 10 Gbps Ethernet rings and on its other, via the D/A and A/D, side with the VLC and the mmWave modules through a switch and/or splitter/combiner.

2) A user equipment including a 5G NR baseband processing server hosts a signal analysing software and a USRP. This 5G NR baseband software can process the received signal from the USRP and perform the OFDM demodulation, channel estimation and zero forcing equalization to obtain the symbols. The USRP device connects to the 5G NR baseband processing server through 2*10Gigabit cable. The USRP device handles the input signal from the mmWave and VLC RX module. It converts the received 3.48 GHz IF signal to baseband signal and delivers to the data processing server.

3) mmWave TX and RX modules generates and receives 40GHz RF signals respectively.

4) VLC Tx/Rx modules.

5) To make mmWave TX and RX modules work properly, a LO generator is used to provide 13GHz signal to them.

6) 10MHz reference signal is provided to the 13GHz LO generator and the USRP device separately.

The system setup parameters including the power levels, modulation schemes, bandwidth and carrier frequencies of these six main components are configured separately for the VLC and mmWave measurement campaign.

Figure 2: VLC Link

As for the VLC link, RRLH generates a signal with centre IF frequency of 15 MHz and power of around -43 dBm from 15 MHz RF port. Then the signal is amplified to a proper power level and spitted by the switch into 4 VLC panels. The red coloured line in above diagram represents RF cable with SMA connector. The VLC modulator inside each VLC panel is designed to accept at much higher input power. Generally, the higher input power the between signal quality is for VLC modulator. However, there is protective input power for VLC to prevent VLC modulator being damaged. So, input power to

VLC panel should be no more than -6 dBm. In order to achieve good signal quality, two stage amplifiers are required to provide -6 dBm power level signal to VLC panel. In addition, to cope with uncertain cable attenuation, an adjustable attenuator is plugged between the two amplifiers.

Figure 3: mmWave Link

As for the mmWave link, RRLH generates signal with centre frequency of 3.48 GHz from 3.48 GHz RF port at -27dBm power. In addition to the signal path, mmWave system requires a separate 13 GHz reference signal. This is generated by the external frequency source which is driven by RRLH 10 MHz reference signal. It is noted that the deep green coloured lines in this diagram represent high frequency cable. The remaining red coloured lines represent sub-6 GHz cable. And the transmitted signal parameters for mmWave and VLC link is listed in the Table 1.

Table 1: Transmitted Signal Parameters

Parameter	mmWave link	VLC Link
RF Carrier frequency (Hz)	60GHz or 40 GHz	Visible Light 400-800 THz
IF Carrier frequency (Hz)	3.48GHz	15MHz
Transmitted power out of RRLH (dBm)	-27	-45
Actual Bandwidth (MHz)	100	10
Modulation	64QAM	QPSK
RX USRP Gain (dB)	0	0
Cable loss (dB)	3	3

During the measurement campaign, the mmWave and VLC link transmitter parameters are fixed for all the scenarios while the transmission distance, angel and location are varied.

The synchronization clock system is working with that RRLH is to provide the 10 MHz reference signal for both UE and mmWave module. The Figure 4: presents a diagram for 10 MHz reference distribution.

Figure 4: 10MHz Reference Distribution

IV. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

This section describes the methodology used to practically evaluate both the coverage and localisation performance of the IoRL system within a home sitting room scenario. For Coverage tests, a live feed readout program (MobaXterm) on the user terminal records the Error Vector magnitude (EVM) of the signal at various positions within the indoor environment. The investigation involves collecting Received Signal Strength (RSS) data, using a custom python code within the user terminal to evaluate the VLC localisation performance. The RSS data provides a position estimate and determines the resultant error given by the Euclidean distance between the estimated and true position through offline processing. This study examines downlink transmission only such that the IoRL transmitters are fixed to the RRLHs, while the mobile receiver module requires manual re-positioning.

The home environment consists of laminate wooden flooring, a leather sofa and a pair of wooden chairs around the edge. During the measurement campaign, an aluminium profile rig of dimensions (2.5m*2.5m*2.2m) concerning L*W*H provides a non-intrusive method to support and mount all required IoRL hardware. The practical system setup is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: IoRL Home Demo Setup

A. VLC coverage

For each RRLH, the communication light source's centre point is mapped onto a floor-level cm grid using a plumb line. This centre point is designated the respective RRLH origin. The VLC photodiode receiver module is placed on the origin, with the photodiode facing directly upwards, in a vertical orientation.

The received signals EVM measurements are recorded at 6cm spacings, up to 54cm, from the origin at each 45-degree angle across the floor. EVM Measurements are left to stabilise between positioning the Receiver and performing the data recording. Notably, due to a long focal length of the lens used to focus the received light, a minor horizontal translation from the origin causes the received light path to 'miss' the receiver photodiode entirely, thus eliminating any received signal. Consequently, a custom gimbal houses the Receiver for all VLC measurements. The gimbal maintains the receiver photodiode's centre point position along the 2D floor grid while providing a means to angle the Receiver towards the respective light source, thereby maintaining LOS.

Figure 6: Remote Radio Light Head

B. mmWave coverage

This study measures the performance of a single mmWave polarised horn antenna. The antenna, mounted to the side of a RRLH, faces directly down. Taking the centre point of the Horn antenna vertically down to floor level formed the grid's origin. The grids x and y axes are made about the horn antennas orientation to maintain the polarised antennas' alignment. To examine both a NLOS and LOS scenario, the Receiver module is placed along the grid with a vertical and angled orientation, respectively, using the gimbal. EVM Measurements are left to stabilise between positioning the Receiver and performing the data recording. These tests are carried out at floor level and a second tabletop height of 0.7m from floor level, with the transmitting antenna, then angled to 30 degrees and 40 degrees from its vertical axis. Re-angling of the transmission antenna maintains the same origin point about the antennas base. Throughout these angled transmitter experiments, the Receiver was used in both a vertical and angled orientation.

C. VLC Location Experiments

Similarly, to the VLC coverage experiment, the 4 RRLH VLC sources' centre point positions are mapped to a cm grid both at floor and tabletop height of 0.7m using a plumbline.

An initial vertical reference measurement is taken at each RRLH centre point to determine the vertical attenuation. The measured data consists of a series of power reference signals to determine the signals RSS. At every designated position along the 2D grid, the Receiver collects individual measurements sequentially from each RRLH. Due to occlusion, the receiver module must be angled towards each RRLH to establish LOS.

D. Estimated Measurement Errors

Throughout the measurement campaign, a laser range tool, the Leica DISTO D2 with a tolerance of +/- 1.5mm provides a reference for all mmWave grid layouts and vertical height measurements. Practical errors present themselves primarily in the positioning and angling of the Receiver module and the use of a plumb line for centre point positioning. Manual positioning of the Receiver using a crosshair provides at maximum an estimated +/- 1 mm tolerance, whereas angles are determined using a protractor with an estimated +/- 1-degree precision. Repeated Plumb line measurements determine the precision to be an estimated +/- 1 mm.

E. Human exposure to time-varying electric, magnetic and electromagnetic fields Experiments

1) Background

EMF experimental procedure consisted of simulating the EMF exposure using simulation tools and then validating the simulations using field measurements within a restricted area to estimate the exposure throughout the room.

The International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) offers scientific guidance and advice on the health and environmental effects of non-ionizing radiation (NIR) to protect people and the environment from harmful NIR exposure. Nonionizing radiation refers to electromagnetic radiation such as infrared, ultraviolet, light and radio waves.

The electromagnetic spectrum comprising the frequency range from 100 kHz to 300 GHz is called High Frequency (HF) with mmWave corresponding to a range of frequencies located between 30 to 300 GHz (10mm to 1mm wavelengths). Various applications are emerging to this band, including imaging and monitoring systems, and wireless telecommunications. The dangerous effect of HF exposure to human health and safety is the heating of exposed tissue. High frequency fields can penetrate into the body causing vibration of charged or polar molecules inside. So, the higher the frequency the lower the penetration depth.

2) Computational Electromagnetics

There are a lot of methods of calculation with varying degrees of complexity and accuracy. For the exposure assessment, it is advised to use simplest appropriate method. The choice is highly dependent on the field region in which the points of investigation are located in relation to the radiating source [15].

The required data put in order of the growing level of accuracy of the exposure assessment by the calculation are the following:

- Operating frequency;
- Distance to the transmitting antenna;

- Maximum equivalent isotropic radiated power (EIRP).

The next step in approving accuracy is obtaining radiation patterns of the transmitting antenna. A complete knowledge of the radiating sources is not fully needed when taken measurements if the equipment covers the full range of frequencies and knowing at least the range of frequencies to be measured. However, if the measurements are made with wideband equipment (without frequency selection or shaped response), the results of such measurement will be conservative, because it requires the use of the limit value, which is more restrictive. In all cases of measurements, the information concerning the radiating sources is very helpful and makes the measurements more accurate and reliable.

The following data are very helpful during measurements (for each radiating source):

- operating frequency – this allows use of a probe that has a band covering all operating frequencies;
- distance to the transmitting antenna – this allows one to determine the field region (for each operating frequency) and to choose a proper measurement procedure;
- maximum equivalent radiated power (ERP) – this allows estimation of the required dynamic range of the measurement equipment and the expected levels of the measured values;
- whether the antennas are operating at the maximum transmitter power at the time of the measurements;
- modulation characteristics – especially pulsed, intermittent or continuous operation.

Usually this information can be obtained from the documentation of the transmitting systems. Some data can be obtained during the site inspection (e.g., distances to the transmitting antennas, operating frequencies based on the types and sizes of the transmitting antennas) [15].

I. Measurements of electromagnetic fields

As part of the evaluation process that was planned, software modelling took place. This section explains the choice of software, preparing of the simulation model and yielded results.

3) Modelling

I. Software selection

There are two electromagnetic simulation software packages were considered, FEKO and WinProp from Altair.

FEKO is a comprehensive computational electromagnetics (CEM) software that is widely used in the automobile, defence, aerospace and telecommunication industries. FEKO offers several frequency and time domain EM solvers, including MoM and FDTD. Hybridization of these approaches allows an efficient analysis of a broad spectrum of EM problems, including RF components and biomedical systems, microstrip circuits, the placement of antennas on electrically large structures, antennas, and the calculation of scattering as well as the investigation of electromagnetic compatibility (EMC).

FEKO and WinProp are used globally across multiple industries including aerospace, communications, automotive, defence, and consumer electronics to reduce the time-to-

market. FEKO addresses the widest set of high-frequency electromagnetics applications. It allows teams to optimize wireless connectivity including 5G. Moreover, it ensures electromagnetic compatibility (EMC), and scattering analysis and perform radar cross section (RCS).

Due to the complex nature of near field, a software simulation is preferred over measurements. In the near field, the EM field structure could also be highly inhomogeneous, and there could also be substantial variations from the plane-wave impedance of 377 ohms. That maybe there it would be almost pure electric (E) fields in some regions and almost pure magnetic (H) fields in others. Exposures in the near field are more difficult to specify, because both fields must be measured and because their field patterns are more complex.

Full wave analysis techniques (e.g. methods requiring Maxwell's equations to be solved anywhere) are essentially used when high accuracy is desired for the evaluation of RF fields, for example for RF field strength, power density or SAR evaluation in source region I (the reactive near-field of the antenna(s)) where ray tracing methods cannot be employed with sufficient accuracy. An accurate and realistic numerical model of the antenna shall be created for a full wave field analysis.

Method of Moments (MoM) or finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) method is used to numerically solve integral equation formulations of Maxwell's equations. In principle, the radiated electromagnetic fields are obtained by following a two-step procedure.

a) First, structures which are represented with a mesh are replaced by equivalent currents. A matrix is derived which represents the effect of each element/segment on each other segment/element and the surface currents are solved.

b) Secondly, these currents are integrated to obtain the electric and magnetic fields at the points of interest.

II. Simulation Model preparation

Two models were prepared for each of the two components of the chosen Altair's software product: WinProp and FEKO. A model the size of a house, would be very computationally expensive for FEKO, if the solver of choice was method of moments. That is not the case for WinProp, which uses ray tracing as a method of solving. Therefore, the idea was to use a suitable approach to compute complex near field – method of moments, and ray tracing method for the far field region.

Figure 7: Detailed model of home scenario

III. RESULTS OF FIELD TESTS

This section provides all the different field tests that was carried out and their results. mmWave and VLC were tested vertical down to determine, which RHL provides the most coverage area. Both were angled towards the transmitter at 30 and 40 degrees to see if there are any improvements in the coverage area. In addition, the tests took place at to different heights at ground level and at 70 cm distance from the RHL. This was to see how if there would be any improvements in their EVMs.

A. VLC Coverage Results

The photodiode receiver was not angled towards the communication LED with illumination LEDs off. As illustrated in Figure 8, the results show the coverage for 4 VLC LED TXs EVM test at 2m distance from the transmitter and the Rx photodiode angle vertically up. The best performing radio light head (RLH) is RLH A, which provide a coverage area of radius 0.3m. A dramatic increase in EVM is observed when the coverage exceeds 0.3 m×0.3 m.

Figure 8: Four VLC TX LEDs pointing vertically down and Rx PD Non-Angled (pointing vertically up), EVM Test results at ground level

The results of each of the 4 VLC LED TXs coverage is shown in Figure 9. The test was conducted at 2m distance with illumination LEDs off and Rx PD angled towards the communication LED. The best performing RLH is A, as it provides a coverage area of a radius of 0.5m.

Figure 9: 4 Four VLC TX LEDs pointing vertically down and Rx PD Angled towards Tx, EVM Test results at ground level

According to 27 testing areas in an illumination area which is, the localization performance is evaluated by the positioning error (PE) using VLC and adjusting the receiver PD and lens to face the communications LED. The distribution of PE is first plotted shown in Figure 10, the orange sign represents the estimated points and the blue sign represents the test points, respectively, where the lowest PE was 0.55 cm and the highest is 11.94cm with an average of 5.28cm, this is shown in Table 1 below. An enhanced RSS positioning algorithm [2], which is an Artificial Intelligence (AI)- based algorithm was used to figure out the optimum position of four Remote Light Heads reduce the location error of measurements taken in a grid of points within the coverage area. Beside that, the cumulative distribution function (CDF) curves of the estimated points is then plotted in Figure 11. It can be found that the current experimental testbed can reach a positioning accuracy of 10 cm at the confidence of 81.48 %.

Table 2: VLC Location Error

Min PE (cm)	Max PE (cm)	Mean PE (cm)
0.55	11.94	5.28

Figure 10: Distribution of test points and estimated points

Figure 11: CDF of position error (<10CM)

Figure 11, shows the cumulative distribution function (CDF)

plot of position error (<10cm), where 81.48% estimated position error is less than 10cm.

C. mmWave Downlink Coverage Results

1) mmWave Transmit Antenna Pointing Vertically Down

The results shown in Figure 12, the coverage for one mmWave Tx's EVM test at height 0.7m above the ground (1.3m from the Tx antenna). The test was conducted with/without Rx antenna angled towards the Tx antenna, while the Tx pointing vertically down.

(a) Without angling Rx toward Tx antenna

(b) With angling Rx toward Tx antenna

Figure 12: One mmWave TXs, receiver at 0.7m above ground EVM Test

The EVM in most of the coverage region was $\leq 8\%$ making it suited for 64-QAM transmission (for 4-QAM this is 12% and for 16-QAM this is 10%). The propagation in the x direction was greater than in the y direction. As x direction was 1.2m and y direction was 0.8m, this was due to the physical construction of the PCB Horn antenna where the horn slant is only applied in the x direction and not in the y direction.

Note: the antenna is polarised in one direction so the transmit and receive antennas must be oriented in the same direction, so the polarisations are aligned with each other, otherwise, the reception will be poor.

The sample results in Figure 13 shows the results of the coverage for one mmWave TXs EVM test at ground level (2.1m from Tx antenna). The test was conducted with/without Rx antenna angled towards the Tx antenna, while the Tx pointing vertically down.

(a) Without angling Rx toward Tx antenna

(b) With angling Rx toward Tx antenna

Figure 13: One mmWave TXs, receiver at 0m ground level EVM Test

The EVM in most of the coverage region was $\leq 8\%$ making it suited for 64-QAM transmission. The results show that angling the Rx towards Tx antenna shows better EVM than non-angled. The performance was also observed to improve when the receiver is placed on the table at 0.7m. This was due to the shrouding effect of the table to reflections from the floor.

2) mmWave Transmit Antenna Point 30° from Vertical about antenna y-axis

The transmit antenna is angled along the room in x direction by 30 degrees and the receiving antenna directed towards the transmitting antenna producing a coverage area of at least 1.6m in both x and y direction as shown in Figure 14b. The receiver is restricted without directing to 0.8m in the x direction and 1.2m in the y direction. These were measurements taken on 17th September 2020.

(a) Without angling Rx toward Tx antenna

(b) With angling Rx toward Tx antenna

Figure 14: One mmWave TXs angled at 30°, receiver at 0m above ground EVM Test

The results were taken again on the 22nd September after processing the data as shown in Figure 15, the new results were unexpected as it was better. However, this shows that the performance of the mmWave system is dependent on external factors which could not be identified. As the same exact testbeds were used.

(a) Without angling Rx toward Tx antenna

(b) With angling Rx toward Tx antenna

Figure 15: One mmWave TXs angled at 30, receiver at 0m above ground EVM Test

The measurements were tested once more, where the transmitting antenna was angled at 30 degrees, but at 0.7m height above the ground as shown in Figure 16.

(a) Without angling Rx toward Tx antenna

(b) With angling Rx toward Tx antenna

Figure 16: One mmWave TXs angled at 30°, receiver at 0.7m above ground EVM Test

The performance of the mmWave system does improve with the Rx angling towards the Tx antenna and it improves near the location of the Tx antenna.

3) mmWave Transmit Antenna Point 40° from Vertical about antenna y-axis

The transmit antenna is angled along the room in x direction by 40 degrees and the receiving antenna directed towards the transmitting antenna producing a coverage area of at least 1.6m in both x and y direction as shown in Figure17.

(a) Without angling Rx toward Tx antenna

(b) With angling Rx toward Tx antenna

Figure 17: One mmWave TXs angled at 40°, receiver at 0m above ground EVM Test

The results shown in Figure 17, shows that the performance of the mmWave system does improve with Tx angling at 40 degrees.

IV. MMWAVE EMF EXPOSURE TEST RESULTS

Due to the size of the simulation model and frequencies involved, WinProp was used for the main simulations and these results are shown below.

1) Dominant electric field

In ProMan, a combination of two result files is possible to get a result file, which contains the maximum, the minimum or the mean value of the two selected result files. To demonstrate direct comparisons between different transmitters and frequencies, combination of maximum value for each individual transmitter is done in this section (as described presently).

Figure 18: Single mmWave E-Field strength for all vertical prediction planes (most left: 1.29 m; middle: 1.5 m; most right: 3.10 m). V/m linear scale

To set the scene and for better understanding of prediction planes see Figure 18 The left-most image illustrates the vertical top-down distribution of energy of the lone mmWave transmitter modelled in the home. The absolute peak of the electric field strength is below 11 V/m, and this located at the immediate excitation of the antenna, or even at the core of source placement. However, as the distance increases, the intensity of the electric field drops significantly and we can estimate that at the beginning of the far field region, values are in the range of below 2 V/m (see vertical prediction plane in Figure 19).

Figure 19: Single mmWave E-Field strength for the first vertical prediction plane. V/m linear scale

Figure 20 demonstrates another vertical prediction plane of electric field distribution per transmitter in V/m, whilst Figure 21 illustrates outcomes of power in logarithmic scale in dBm.

Figure 20: Indoors 3D view of four mmWave transmitters at height of 1.8 m

Figure 21: Four mmWave transmitters power level at height of 1.8 m. Log scale

Figure 22: Simulation of E-Field strength for 4 mmWave Tx and 40 additional Tx at height of 0.70m

2) Total electric field

To show the total field in relation to exposure limits, summation of exposure ratios is performed. It is important to determine whether, in situations of simultaneous exposure to fields of different frequencies, these exposures are additive in their effects.

For thermal considerations, relevant above 100 kHz [8], the following two requirements should be applied to the field levels:

$$\sum_{i=100\text{ kHz}}^{1\text{ MHz}} \left(\frac{E_i}{c}\right)^2 + \sum_{i>1\text{ MHz}}^{300\text{ GHz}} \left(\frac{E_i}{E_{L,i}}\right)^2 \leq 1$$

and

$$\sum_{i=100\text{ kHz}}^{1\text{ MHz}} \left(\frac{H_i}{d}\right)^2 + \sum_{j>1\text{ MHz}}^{300\text{ GHz}} \left(\frac{H_j}{H_{L,j}}\right)^2 \leq 1$$

Where

- E_i = the electric field strength at frequency i ;
- $E_{L,i}$ = the electric field reference level
- H_j = the magnetic field strength at frequency j ;
- $H_{L,j}$ = the magnetic field reference level
- $c = 610/f$ V/m (f in MHz) for occupational exposure and $87/f^{(1/2)}$ V/m for general public exposure; and
- $d = 1.6/f$ A/m (f in MHz) for occupational exposure and $0.73/f$ for general public exposure

The total field strength was calculated for each of the device frequencies at the worst-case location just below the IoRL antennas and compared to the exposure limits and the

calculated Exposure Ratios, Table 3. The total contribution to Exposure Ratio from all frequencies rounds up to 0.099 (ER <1) so this is considerably below the ICNIRP limits.

Table 3: Summation of Exposure Ratio contributors (in-phase constructive interference at a point – at the antenna)

Frequency (MHz)	868	1850	2400	5000	40000
Sum E-Field	0.53 V/m	0.12 V/m	15.84 V/m	4.52 V/m	9.791 V/m
E-Field limit	40.51 V/m	59.14 V/m	61 V/m	61 V/m	61 V/m
Individual contribution to Exposure Ratio	0.0001712	0.000004117	0.06743	0.005491	0.02576

Figure 23: Summed broadband electric field strength at a point for all heights, in a vertical line, directly below mmWave antenna

Figure 23 shows the total field strength in the region directly below mmWave antenna, when all devices are summed assuming the worst case that they are all in-phase (constructive interference). It can be observed that there is a spike at 1.15 meters, where majority of IoT devices are vertically located although even higher field strength is observed, as the height approaches the mmWave radiation source height. Comparing the blue and orange lines in that graph, shows that the 40 GHz contribution to the total electric field increases with elevation. It should be noted that this is a somewhat worst-case calculation and that in reality total field strengths are likely to be much lower, which was observed during the measurements detailed below.

3) Measurements

a) Measurement Instrument selection

The instrument used to perform the above measurements was a NARDA Broadband Field Meter NBM-520. The NARDA Broadband Field Meter NBM-520 is a popular instrument for measuring non-ionizing radiation within the frequency range from 100 kHz to 60 GHz (depending on the probe used). Probes for various measurement applications are connected to the NBM-520 basic unit. Flat frequency response probes are also available, and shaped probes that evaluate the

field according to a specific human safety standard. These probes are calibrated separately from the measuring instrument. Also, they include a non-volatile memory containing the probe parameters and calibration data. Therefore, they could be used with any instrument in the NBM-500 family without any lack in calibration accuracy.

The NBM-520 do measurements for human safety purposes, mostly in workplace environments, where high electric or magnetic field strengths are expected. Also, it can be used to determine the electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) of devices and equipment. Examples:

- Measuring field strengths as part of general safety regulations
- Measuring the field strengths around transmitting and radar equipment to establish safety zones and for monitoring during operations
- Measuring the field strength emanating from mobile phone repeaters and satellite communications systems to ensure compliance with human safety limit values
- Measuring the field strength in the industrial workplace, such as tempering, RF heating, drying and plastics welding equipment.
- Field strength measurements in absorber chambers and TEM cells.

The measurement probe was selected to be EF4091. The probe contains three orthogonally arranged dipoles with detector diodes. The diode voltages each correspond to the RMS value of the spatial components.

The isotropic measurement result is obtained by addition within the probe. The probe detects electric fields from 40 MHz up to 40 GHz. This frequency range covers almost the entire range of high frequency communications, right up to mobile radio and satellite links. The linearity and sensitivity of the probe ensure its suitability for checking human safety limit values in the occupational and general public environments.

b) Measurements – procedures and methodologies

The aluminium frame on which the RRLH controller and RRLHs are fitted is shown in Figure 24 in order for the mmWave antenna location to coincide with the mmWave antenna location used in the EM radio simulations, as shown in Figure 21 and Figure 22.

(a) At 0.7 m height

(b) At 1.2 m height

Figure 24: Location of RRLH Controller and RRLHs for EM Radiation Measurements

The location of the source and RF propagation path during measurements were considered to minimize the influence of the body on the result. A check was made, as per the manufacturer's specifications for the minimum distance between the measurement probe tip and the body of the "operator", as well as to any reflecting object. Non-conductive materials were used, to secure and position measuring device in place. For handheld measurements, the uncertainty due to the scattering of the RF field by the surveyor's body was minimized by:

- holding the probe or antenna away from the surveyor's body (a separation of at least 50 cm should be maintained between the measurement antenna or isotropic probe and the surveyor's body);
- pointing the probe towards the source;
- ensuring that the surveyor's body is not along the direct line of propagation between the source and the measurement probe (either in front of or behind).

Figure 26: Location of mmWave Antenna

The Intelligent Home IP Gateway, Layer 2 Processor and DRAN was located on one trolley as shown in Figure 27a, whilst the Viavi User Test Terminal was located on a second trolley, as shown in Figure 27b. The EM radiation level measurement device, shown in Figure 25, can operate independent to the Test End User Terminal.

(a) Intelligent Home IP Gateway, Layer 2 Processor & DRAN

(b) Viavi Test End User Terminal

Figure 27: IoRL Head-end and End User systems

Figure 25: EM Radiation Level Measurement device

The system was set to broadcast at full power. Measurements were performed at three heights: 0.7, 1.2 and 1.8 meters above floor level. Theoretically, at 1.8 m, the colleagues collecting data are in the Near Field region of the antenna.

Two measurement procedures were performed: with the IoRL system ON and OFF. Additionally, space averaging, peak and time averaging measurements were done.

Space averaging Discreet spatial measurements were performed for each horizontal prediction plane, averaging over a 3x3 grid (9 points, the point in the middle of grid, marked as X5, is located directly below mmWave transmitter – see Figure28 below), with 10 cm distance between each measurement point.

Figure 28: Diagram of measurement grid

c) Results

(1) mmWave System turned ON

1. Time averaging peak measurement over 6 minutes, directly below transmitting antenna (probe physically in contact with antenna)

Result is listed below:

a. 5.74 V/m

2. Spatial averaging measurement over 9 points consisting of square 3 x 3 grid, with distance of 10 cm between points and middle of grid directly under mmWave antenna, at each height.

Results are listed in Table 4 below:

Table 4: Measured electric field strength (V/m), spaced averaged, with mmWave transmitter turned on

Meas. Point Height	Height 1 == 0.7 m	Height 2 == 1.2 m	Height 3 == 1.8 m
X1	1.02	1.24	1.61
X2 Averages	0.92	1.15	1.62
X3 Averages	0.85	1.05	1.69
X4 Averages	0.87	1.05	1.75
X5 Averages	0.82	1.06	1.8
X6 Averages	0.82	1.08	1.79
X7 Averages	0.90	1.08	1.70
X8 Averages	0.88	1.05	1.68
X9 Final Average	0.89	1.06	1.65

* Measurements were taken in the following sequence: X1, X2, X3, X6, X5, X4, X7, X8, X9.

3. Absolute peak measurement directly below transmitting antenna (probe physically in contact with antenna)
a. 6.44 V/m

(2) mmWave System turned OFF

1. Time averaging peak measurement over 6 minutes, directly below transmitting antenna (probe physically in contact with antenna)

Result is listed below:
a. 0.69 V/m

2. Spatial averaging measurement over 9 points consisting of square 3 x 3 grid, with distance of 10 cm between points and middle of grid directly under mmWave antenna, at each height.

Results are listed in Table 5 below:

Table 5: Measured electric field strength (V/m), spaced averaged, with mmWave transmitter turned off

Meas. Point Height	Height 1 == 0.7 m	Height 2 == 1.2 m	Height 3 == 1.8 m
X1	0.63	0.82	1.22
X2 Averages	0.47	0.74	1.29
X3 Averages	0.54	0.66	1.32
X4 Averages	0.60	0.60	1.25
X5 Averages	0.56	0.60	1.32
X6 Averages	0.54	0.63	1.34
X7 Averages	0.58	0.64	1.19
X8 Averages	0.58	0.67	1.18
X9 Final Average	0.57	0.67	1.21

* Measurements were taken in the following sequence: X1, X2, X3, X6, X5, X4, X7, X8, X9.

V. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

a. VLC coverage

Results from VLC measurements shows that the coverage has a diameter of about 0.6 m and maximum propagation distance of 2m. This limited coverage was attributed to the physical construction of the PD sensor housing. The variation in performance between communication LEDs A, B, C and D was attributed to the variability in transmitted light intensities between them.

When angling the PD receiver towards the transmit LED, this improves the quality of the received signal so that the coverage has a diameter of about 1m and maximum propagation distance of 2m, as shown in Figure 8. Again, the variation in performance between communication LEDs A, B, C and D was attributed to the variability in transmitted light intensities between them.

b. VLC location

Received signal strength results have also been used to locate positions with a minimum location error of 3.5cm and 80% of all location measurement errors of less than 10cm.

c. mmWave Coverage

Results from mmWave 64 QAM transmissions have shown that for a single polarization transmit antenna pointing vertically down, there was a reasonably consistent coverage area of about two meters diameter at 0.7m above ground (1.3m from transmit antenna) with and without angling the receive antenna towards the transmit antenna, as shown in Figure 12. There was a slight improvement of results when angling the receive antenna towards the transmit antenna. The asymmetry of the coverage performance was attributed to a glass door on one side of the coverage area, which produced mmWave reflections that impaired the performance of the receiver. An improved design of the mmWave, which more effectively processes multipath propagations, would provide more symmetric coverage performance results.

Results from mmWave 64 QAM transmissions have shown that for a single polarization transmit antenna pointing vertically down, there was a patchy coverage area of about two meters diameter at 0.0m above ground (2.0m from transmit antenna) with and without angling the receive antenna towards the transmit antenna, as shown in Figure 13. There was no noticeable improvement of results when angling the receive antenna towards the transmit antenna. Again, the asymmetry of the coverage performance was attributed to a glass door on one side of the coverage area, which produced mmWave reflections that impaired the performance of the receiver.

When the transmit antenna was rotated towards the receive antenna at 30 degrees from the vertical, a patchy coverage area was measured, which has a width of 2.0m and length of at least 1.6m at 0.0m above ground level when the receive antenna is rotated towards the transmit antenna, as shown in Figure 14b. When the receive antenna was not angled towards the transmit antenna, the coverage area has been reduced to a width and length of about 1m, as shown in Figure 14a. When the same experiment was repeated five days later on 22nd

September, similar performance coverage area results were obtained but with different patchy patterns, as shown in Figure 15a and 15b, the difference of which were not able to be explained.

When the transmit antenna was rotated towards the receive antenna at 30 degrees from the vertical, a uniform coverage area was measured, which has a width of 2.0m and length of more than 2.0m (6m as measured in laboratory) at 0.7m above ground level when the receive antenna is rotated towards the transmit antenna, as shown in Figure 16b. When the receive antenna was not angled towards the transmit antenna, the coverage area has the same width but a reduced length of about 1m, as shown in Figure 16a.

When the transmit antenna was rotated towards the receive antenna at 30 degrees from the vertical, a patchy coverage area was measured, which has a width of 2.0m and length of 2.0m at 0.0m above ground level when the receive antenna is rotated towards the transmit antenna, as shown in Figure 17b. When the receive antenna was not angled towards the transmit antenna, the coverage area has a reduced width of 1.6m and reduced length of about 1m, as shown in Figure 17a.

d. mmWave EM Exposure

The measurements and simulations are compared in Figure 29 and Figure 30. The orange and blue line in Figure 29 denote calculations that are based on the simulated data, and were done assuming perfect in-phase constructive interference, as this represent the worst-case scenario possible, although it is recognised that this is not realistic in practice and the measurements confirm this.

Figure 30: Comparisons between measured and simulated results (summation of electric field strengths, assuming in-phase constructive interference)

Figure 29: Comparisons between measured and simulated results (Dominant electric field)

In Figure 30, the measurements are compared to the simulated dominant field. This shows a much better comparison. At a height of 2 m, where the mmWave transmitter is located, there is a very good match, with both the predicted and measured field strengths being about 6.4 V/m, for the mmWave and background radiation. The main difference is between the measurement and simulation of the background field strengths, with the measurements average about 1 V/m and the simulations 2 V/m over the range of heights.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The level of performance that was measured for the 5G VLC communications system is more suited to Personal Communication applications such as that required for transmission to passengers on seating within aircraft and trains or for controlling home devices such as washing machines and TVs from smart phones. Performance of the VLC communications system would have to increase propagation distance by a factor of 3 to 6m and increase the coverage area by a factor of six to 6 meters for it to be a general-purpose communications competitor to the mmWave communication system in indoor environments. Furthermore, enhancements to the PD receiver would also be required so that it has the multidirectional photo sensing properties of a fly's eye, which could possibly be achieved using a Fresnel lens at the receiver.

The level of performance that was measured for the 5G mmWave communications system has shown the viability of a 5G networked home since just four mmWave radio heads would be required to provide sufficient coverage for a family sized sitting room, whilst also providing sufficient numbers of mmWave radio access point to be able to measure location. The best position of these radio heads are at the four corners of the room pointing at 30 degrees from the vertical towards the centre of the room. The transmit antenna would be required to be enhanced so that it is circular or polarized or at the least provide both vertical and horizontal polarized antennas transmitters. Further experiments need to be performed from four transmit antennas to show that this man-made multipath environment does away with the requirement of angling the receive antenna towards any one transmits

antenna to obtain improved performance, which would be physically impossible to achieve when simultaneously transmitting the same radio signal from four different transmit antennas at the same time. Implementation of the mmWave Time Division Multiplexing return channel means that the next phase of the measurement campaign will consist of measuring the accuracy of Time Difference of Arrival location.

The ICNIRP exposure ratio calculated from the total field strength contributions from the simulated results estimated that the exposure ratio was just less than 0.1 (see Table 3), with any value below one being compliant with the ICNIRP limits, and this was therefore considerably below the ICNIRP limits. The measurement field strengths were slightly lower than the simulations and reasonably similar to the simulated results.

This work gives an indication of the estimated levels of risk associated with the scenarios modelled. However, this work should not be taken as any kind of approval for such products to be placed for sale on the market. Any manufacturers placing such products on the market should go through the necessary product approval processes to meet the necessary regulations and standards, including any national standards and guidance, and perform their own assessments of their specific system specifications.

International Committee on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) guidelines are used worldwide, either directly or as the basis for national regulations. These ICNIRP levels have been used in this report as a reference level. It is recognised that there are some variations in some national regulations, and these should be considered for any product manufacturers looking to take products to market.

The emissions from other wireless devices in addition to IoRL were included in the calculations to give estimates of other background field strength levels. However, this report is only assessing the potential impact of the IoRL devices with respect to human exposure limits, not any other wireless devices.

Some calculations use a number of worst-case assumptions, such as the contributions from all devices being in-phase and all with 100% activity. These results should not be taken as a representation of actual field strengths that would be experienced in practice. Measurements were made of actual devices which considered how the devices operate in practice and demonstrated lower levels of field strength as expected.

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